

Neutronic Analysis of a Small Lead-Cooled Reactor using OpenMC Code

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803520

ABSTRACT

Lead-cooled reactors are among the fourth-generation designs that are at advanced levels of maturity and have recently garnered large interest motivated by growing energy demands. These designs are inherently and passively safe, promise improved economics, and waste minimization and re-utilization. In this study, a fast spectrum small modular reactor concept is presented, with its core geometry defined by first principles thermal-hydraulics calculations, followed by a neutronic analysis of the hot core. A series of simulations are performed using OpenMC Monte Carlo code, at beginning-of-life and middle-of-life, to characterize neutron flux, control rod and shutdown rod worths, kinetic parameters, reactivity feedback coefficients, and power distributions. A burnup calculation is made using the available predictor integrator algorithm in OpenMC using JEFF3.2 cross-section data library. The benefit of using this methodology for reactor design is discussed.

Keywords: Small Modular Reactor, Generation IV, OpenMC Monte Carlo Code, Burnup Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs) are Generation IV concepts that use liquid lead (lead–bismuth in a few variants) as the primary coolant and operate in a fast neutron spectrum. Lead as a coolant offers high boiling point, excellent radiation shielding and low reactivity with air/water, enabling low-pressure primary systems and favourable passive safety characteristics. These properties make LFRs attractive for both large central plants and small modular applications. The Generation IV International Forum has identified LFRs as a promising route for long-term sustainability, enhanced safety and high thermal efficiency relative to thermal-spectrum designs [1].

Interest in small modular lead-cooled reactors has grown because liquid lead allows compact integral layouts, strong decay-heat removal paths (passive conduction), and reduced active systems compared with water-cooled small modular reactors (SMRs). LFR designs include ALFRED [2] and ELFR [3] as a joint European Union (EU) project, LFR-AS-30/200 [4] in EU, PEACER [5] and URANUS [6] in South Korea, BREST-OD-300 [7] under construction and SVBR-75/100 [8] under development in Russia, SSTAR [9] and Westinghouse LFR [10] under development in the US, and CLEAR [11] concept in China. In Sweden, Blykalla is currently building an electric prototype with plans for their first-of-a-kind LFR design SEALER-One to reach criticality by 2029 and commercially produce SEALER-55 [12][13] in 2030s.

From a neutronics perspective, LFR core poses distinctive modelling challenges and opportunities. The fast spectrum increases neutron-induced transmutation and breeding potential while reducing moderation-driven feedbacks. Accurate prediction of reactivity and power distribution requires careful treatment of (i) lead's scattering and capture cross-sections (including energy dependence and resonance structure), (ii) the relatively large effect of structural and reflector materials, (iii) temperature and Doppler feedbacks in nitride/oxide fuels, and (iv) uncertainties from impurities and activation in the heavy-metal coolant. Because lead has a high atomic number and complex inelastic scattering, continuous-energy transport methods are often preferred for high-fidelity neutronic design and

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uncertainty quantification. The OECD/NEA LFR [14] benchmark activity recognizes the limited experimental basis for LFR cores and the consequent need for rigorous code-to-code and experiment-to-calculation validation. In this paper, an LFR design based on SEALER is presented, with an analysis of its neutronics and a test of modelling capabilities of the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC [15].

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE REACTOR

The core of this reactor has a design power of 140MWth cooled with molten lead operating between 420°C (inlet) and 550°C (outlet). The reactor is designed to run for 22.5 effective full power years with an open fuel cycle strategy. It comprises 85 fuel assemblies (FA), 6 control rod (CR) assemblies, 6 shutdown (SD) assemblies and 72 reflector assemblies, all enclosed in hex-can wrappers. The power-dense core is packed with 18.6tons of 11.8% enriched uranium nitride (UN) fuel pellets. CR absorber pellets are made of conventional natural boron carbide (B_4C), SD absorber is made of novel tungsten-rhenium diboride ($WReB_2$), that has a theoretical density greater than liquid lead, thereby enabling passive insertion of SD assembly driven by gravity in case of SCRAM [16]. Radial reflectors comprise of yttrium stabilized zirconia (YSZ). To mitigate the effects of fast fluence in core, the fuel clad is made of austenitic 15-15Ti steel, that has proven creep properties. However, it lacks corrosion properties, which is addressed by a protective alumina layer forming Fe-10Cr-4Al-RE steel. In addition, within the fuel rod, zirconium nitride (ZrN) insulators protect the top and bottom of the fuel column, and B_4C acts as lower shield. There are ten integrated helical coil steam generators and pumps in locations surrounding the core for heat extraction and circulation of the coolant. Key reactor design specifications are presented in Table I. Figure 1 and Figure 2 present the radial and axial cross-section of the core and fuel assembly, as plotted in OpenMC.

Table I. Key parameters of the LFR design.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Thermal power	140	MWth
Pressure	1	atm
Fuel element	UN	
U ²³⁵ enrichment	11.8	%wt
Density	12.9 (10% por)	g/cm ³
Fuel rods/assembly	85 and 271	
Active core (dia/hei)	204/130.5	cm/cm
Primary vessel (dia/hei)	420/600	cm/cm
Coolant	Lead	
Inlet temperature	420	°C
Outlet temperature	550	°C
Flow rate	7410	kg/s
Control element	B_4C	
B ¹⁰ enrichment	19.9	%wt
Density	2.5	g/cm ³
Control rods/assembly	19	
Shutdown element	$WReB_2$	
WB ₂ fraction	48	%
Density	12.3	g/cm ³
Shutdown rods/assembly	7	
Reflector element	YSZ	
Density	6.3	g/cm ³
Reflector rods/assembly	37	

Figure 1. Core map of the LFR.

Using the key design parameters (cold geometry (CG) at 25°C), the full power steady-state temperature distributions of the coolant, clad and fuel surfaces are determined analytically from first principles heat transfer inside the central sub-channel. Subsequently the core geometry is updated (hot geometry (HG)) to account for the effect of thermal expansion in all structural materials. These changes in geometry would lead to reactivity variations and neutronic simulations are performed to determine them.

2.1. Thermal-Hydraulics Description

The coolant mass flow rate, given in Table I, assumes a constant average flow through all the 85 fuel assembly coolant channels. Due to peak factors and frictional losses, in reality, flow in the central channel would be larger than in the periphery, so that a uniform temperature profile of coolant outlet is achieved. For sake of conservatism, thermal-hydraulics calculations are conducted on the coolant channel with the maximum power generation. A preliminary OpenMC calculation on cold geometry specifications yields the axial and radial peak factors, as 1.3 and 1.6 respectively. Subsequently, the power generated/peak channel, is used to arrive at temperatures of the bulk coolant, assuming a cosine axial power profile of the fuel rod. Figure 3 shows the bulk coolant, outer and inner cladding, surface and centerline fuel temperature as calculated by a simple 1D heat transfer model, assuming heat conduction across fuel pellet, helium gas gap, cladding, and convection to the coolant. A maximum fuel centerline temperature of 862°C is calculated to be at 10cm above midplane (dashed black line). Using this temperature description, thermal expansion of all elements inside the core are determined, updated specifications are listed in Table II, and hot steady-state neutronic calculations are performed.

Figure 3. Temperature profile along the peak coolant channel in the LFR.

Figure 2. Axial cross section of the fuel assembly.

Table II. Fuel rod bundle specification.

Parameter	Value (CG/HG)	Unit
Fuel rod length	130.5/131.16	cm/cm
Fuel pellet outer diameter	0.812/0.816	cm/cm
Clad inner diameter	0.856/0.863	cm/cm
Clad outer diameter	0.96/0.968	cm/cm
Total clad length	206/207.669	cm/cm
Fuel rod pitch	1.13/1.13	cm/cm

2.2. Steady-State Neutronics

Using this description, a model is developed using OpenMC 0.15.3 along with JEFF3.2 cross-section library [17]. JEFF3.2 is used here as a base case study, as it shows minimal variations compared to other cross-section libraries [18]. A thorough comparison with other libraries will be performed in the future. All the fuel assemblies are assumed to be at the same average hot temperature (900K) without axial or radial distributions. When the core reaches a hot state, a reactivity of 136 ± 12 pcm is removed due to increase in geometry (fuel axial expansion) and Doppler broadening. Firstly, at the beginning-of-life (BOL) of the reactor, the reactivity worths of the CR assembly bank and SD assembly bank are determined by lowering the assemblies into the core from the initial parking position (considered to be at upper endcap). At each lowered position the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) is calculated and corresponding reactivity (ρ in pcm) is determined using Equation (1).

$$\rho = (k_{eff} - 1)/k_{eff} \quad (1)$$

Figure 4 and Figure 10 show the reactivity worth curves for the CR and SD banks with respect to the reactivity at parking position (in the figure U: upper endcap, L: lower endcap, insertion % is within the active zone of the core from top to bottom) at BOL and middle-of-life (MOL). Entire CR bank has a worth of -953 ± 12 pcm (BOL) and -844 ± 12 pcm (MOL), and the SD bank a similar -967 ± 12 pcm (BOL) and -859 ± 12 pcm (MOL). The worth of a single CR assembly is calculated to be around -168 ± 13 pcm (by insertion of one assembly) at BOL and -196 ± 13 pcm at MOL. The worth of 5 CR assemblies when fully

inserted is -777 ± 13 pcm at BOL and is -845 ± 13 pcm at MOL. The shutdown margin (SDM), calculated by completely inserting all control and shutdown assemblies except for 1 CR assembly which is assumed to be stuck, is calculated to be -1756 ± 13 pcm at BOL and -2111 ± 13 pcm at MOL. Typically, to prevent large reactivity insertion due to inadvertent withdrawal of CR, core designers limit reactivity worth of each assembly to be below 0.5\$. At BOL this turns out to be 0.25\$ when fully inserted. Having this knowledge of the CR bank, a position that yields a critical core can be determined, and this is about 40cm below the top-of-active-fuel (TAF). At this position, the axial cross section of the neutron flux in the core is presented in Figure 5. The flux is normalized by the average flux over the core. As expected, it is strong at the centre and decreases outwards radially and axially. The lower shield reduces neutrons below the active zone, however presence of gas plenum above the fuel pellet observes flux extending above the core. This is why the CR and SD have a worth of about 100 ± 12 pcm and 126 ± 12 pcm above active core, respectively (see Figure 4). The axial power profile and radial power distributions are presented in Figure 6 and Figure 7 respectively. At the lower region of the core, the power density is lowered due to the lower shield. While at the upper region, a comparatively higher power density is observed because of back-scattering effect of the coolant, and the profile is skewed from the cosine profile, with a combined peak factor of 2.2.

Figure 4. S-curves of the control and shutdown rod banks at BOL.

Figure 5. Normalized neutron flux in the critical core at BOL.

Figure 6. Axial power profile in the core for different configurations and burnup. C: core critical position.

Figure 7. Radial power distribution in the core at BOL.

2.3. Reactor Burnup Calculations

OpenMC has implemented several transport-coupled depletion strategies and in this study the simple predictor integrator (PI) algorithm is used [19]. The method works by making a key simplification to

solving the Bateman equations, which govern nuclear depletion: it treats the system's transition matrix A as a constant value, specifically using its value from the very beginning of the time step. This assumption allows the Bateman equations to be solved with a direct, exact mathematical formula for that step. The solution for the number densities at the next time point is calculated simply by applying the matrix exponential of this constant matrix (scaled by the time step interval h) to the initial densities. The following depletion steps are considered: [2.5, 2.5, 2.5, 2.5, 1.25, 1.25, 5, 5] years, at full power for a total lifetime of the reactor of 22.5 years. The total burnup at the end-of-life (EOL) is around 60.7MWd/tU. A simplified CASL depletion chain for fast spectrum reactors was used as it results in low runtime without compromising on accuracy [20]. The isotopes included in the chain are as recommended by the VERA depletion benchmark [21].

The k_{eff} evolution, converted to reactivity, is shown in Figure 9. The evolution follows a parabolic path, as expected from a breed and burn type core, where in the first period new fissile material is produced (increasing reactivity), and in the second period fuel is burnt (decreasing reactivity), indicating a conversion ratio > 1 . A peak excess reactivity of 372 ± 12 pcm is observed at MOL after 12.25 years, and CR bank is inserted into the core to counteract the excess. By the EOL, the core reactivity is in excess by 82 ± 13 pcm compared to BOL. The reactivity worth curves of the CR and SD at MOL are given in Figure 10. Knowing this, CR bank is further inserted into the core by about 50cm to 90cm below TAF. Consequently axial and radial power profiles of the core change, and are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 9. There is marginal change in the peak factors. Central channel has slightly higher power generation while outer channels have lower power generation at MOL than at BOL.

Figure 8. Reactivity evolution of the LFR.

Figure 9. Radial power distribution in the core at MOL.

There are several higher order time integrator algorithms in OpenMC. At the time of writing of this paper, calculations with these algorithms were still running and would be presented in the future. OpenMC has two newly implemented stochastic-implicit integrators, SI-CE/LI and SI-LE/QI, that expand upon the existing CE/LI and LE/QI integrators respectively with Stochastic Implicit Euler method. It was shown by a comparative analysis in [20] that SI-CE/LI method outperforms other available methods. So far, one burnup step for SI-CE/LI has been performed for 20,000 particles with a total CPU time of 312h, while entire burnup calculation for all the steps using PI algorithm on the same Intel 12th Gen i9-12900K CPU took 288h. Because of their improved accuracy and efficiency, albeit with increased memory requirements, it is worth investigating how the nuclide inventory and the neutronics parameters vary with these methods. It should be noted that so far all calculations have been performed using OpenMC, and code-to-code benchmark has not been performed for the same design. However, Serpent related calculations performed on SEALER can be found in [12][13].

2.4. Reactor Safety Parameters

The neutron spectrum of the LFR, considering a 500-group and ECCO-1968 energy structure [22], is presented in Figure 11. A peak flux in the order of 10^{13} n/cm²/s is observed in the core, typical for the

nitride type fuel. The kinetic parameters and the reactivity coefficients are important safety parameters for characterizing the dynamic behaviour of the reactor during transients. For the BOL, MOL and EOL fuel nuclide composition obtained from the depletion calculations, adjoint-weighted kinetic parameters: eight-group delayed neutron fractions (β) and effective generation time (Λ_{eff}), are calculated. OpenMC has inbuilt functionality to define the delayed groups and estimate the adjoint-weighted parameters using the iterated fission probability method, like the Serpent2 code [23]. Of the several coefficients, the Doppler coefficient, fuel axial expansion coefficient, core radial expansion coefficient and coolant density coefficient are calculated in this study. These coefficients make larger contribution to overall feedback than other secondary order effects.

Figure 10. S-curves of the control and shutdown rod banks at MOL.

Figure 11. Neutron flux spectrum in the LFR.

Doppler effect, caused by broadening of resonance peaks, provides an immediate response to reactivity. Fuel Doppler constant (K_D) is calculated by varying the temperature of the fuel (as per the data available in the cross-section library) and computing the reactivities as a function of temperature. Doppler coefficient (α_D) is then calculated by a logarithmic fit to the variation of reactivity (ρ) with fuel temperature (T_f). Fuel axial expansion coefficient (α_{ax}) driven by changes in fuel volume also provides an immediate effect. As fuel rods expand axially, they increase absorption of neutrons by the CR along the newly expanded volume. α_{ax} is calculated by modifying geometry of the fuel rods, in response to thermal expansion. Similarly, increasing temperature of the core grid plate (T_{grid}) increases pitch of the fuel assemblies thereby increasing effective core diameter. Negative reactivity is therefore introduced and is the basis for the core radial expansion coefficient (α_{rad}). This is calculated by varying the pitch of the fuel assembly lattice in response to varying T_{grid} . Changes in the coolant density in the core region also result in changes in reactivity, mainly because a temperature increase leads to increase in leakage and spectral hardening which in turn increases parasitic absorption and moderation. This forms the basis for the coolant density coefficient (α_{pb}). This is calculated by changing coolant density corresponding to changing T_{pb} . The coolant void worth ($\Delta\rho_{void}$) is calculated by voiding the active zone (in the unlikely event of lead boiling). The safety parameters of the LFR are listed in Table III.

Table III. Kinetic parameters and reactivity feedback coefficients of the LFR.

Parameter	Value			Unit
	BOL	MOL	EOL	
Λ_{eff}	0.478±0.002	0.431±0.002	0.398±0.001	μs
β_{eff}	716.0±1.6	618.3±1.3	547.4±1.0	pcm
K_D	-735±13	-647±12	-600±12	pcm
α_{ax}	-0.125±0.018	-0.149±0.019	-0.142±0.019	pcm/K
α_{rad}	-0.36±0.050	-0.388±0.046	-0.385±0.050	pcm/K
α_{pb}	0.006±0.001	0.044±0.001	0.029±0.001	pcm/K
$\Delta\rho_{void}$	1010±12	1599±12	1635±13	pcm

2.5. Dynamic System Behaviour

As the reactor is designed with dense liquid lead, in case of an event involving inadvertent control rod movement there is a possibility of it being ejected, and a positive reactivity being inserted, into the core. Because at MOL the k_{eff} is high due to burnup, and accumulated fission gas and products in the fuel matrix could cause large radiological hazard if it were to be damaged, a transient involving unprotected (without SCRAM or shutdown) overpower (UTOP) is studied here. There are system thermal-hydraulic codes, such as SAS4A/SASSYS-1, SIMMER, DYNA-P, FAST to name a few, available for dynamic analysis of fast spectrum reactors. BELLA is a lumped point-kinetics reactor dynamics code developed at KTH and is employed for transient assessments [24]. Uniform discretization of reactivity feedback coefficients is considered for the entire active core without separate axial or radial effects. Impact of coolant temperatures above and below the core is not included for feedbacks. An event assuming ejection of 1 CR assembly, that is worth about 0.2\$ at MOL, in 1s is simulated using BELLA. The results from the simulation are presented in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

Figure 12. Reactivity feedback during UTOP.

Figure 13. Fuel rod temperatures during UTOP.

As seen, the contributions from all but coolant density coefficient counter the positive inserted reactivity. Doppler effect has the largest negative contribution, and is also the quickest to act, followed by fuel axial expansion and core radial expansion. As expected from the positive α_{pb} value in Table III, coolant contributes a small positive reactivity during the transient. The steady-state cladding temperatures reach 620°C with transient peak of 630°C, and fuel temperatures reach 900°C. The cladding temperature data is particularly relevant for subsequent creep rupture. The design demonstrates robust performance under extreme UTOP conditions, preserving a good buffer from fuel melting temperatures of 1600°C.

3. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, analysis of a small lead-cooled fast reactor design was presented. Initial thermal-hydraulic calculations indicated a peak fuel centerline temperature of 862°C and clad outer surface temperature of 550°C. Considering thermal expansion of the core materials, at steady-state full power, a model of the core was developed using OpenMC Monte Carlo code and criticality simulations were run. The evolution of k_{eff} with fuel burnup was calculated using the predictor algorithm and over the 22.5 years of the lifetime a peak reactivity of 372pcm was observed at 12.25 years. Simulations with other higher order algorithms are currently underway and the results would be benchmarked. The CR and SD bank worths were calculated at the beginning and the middle-of-life, and a small reduction was observed. Subsequently, at these instances of time, the reactor kinetic parameters and reactivity feedback coefficients were determined. The inherent safety of the design was demonstrated during a UTOP transient, with negative reactivity feedback being able to maintain sufficient margin to core melting. Dynamic safety assessments during other unprotected transients such as loss-of-flow and loss-of-

heatsink are in progress and will be presented in the future. A critical aspect of LFRs is the minor actinide inventory in the fuel that needs to be burnt to reduce long-lived radio-toxic isotopes. A thorough assessment of nuclear cross-section data library, nuclide inventory, and its impact on radiological consequences will also be performed. With newly implemented methods, OpenMC has demonstrated its capabilities in neutronic assessment of fast reactors, and further studies will supplement the code development activities.

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